

ANALYSIS OF RUSSIAN CULINARY AND BOTANICAL TERMINOLOGY OF CHINESE ORIGIN AMONG AZERBAIJANI RUSSIAN-SPEAKING UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Aims and objectives: This study aims to analyze the current situation of Azerbaijani native Russian-speaking university students regarding their knowledge of culinary and botanical terms of Chinese origin used in the Russian language. The research will focus on identifying the level of familiarity and understanding of these terms among the students and the challenges they face in comprehending them.

Methodology: This study utilized the analytical summary method to identify twenty loanwords of Russian origin. Data was collected through mixed-method research, including questionnaires and interviews. In this paper the Chinese loanwords in the Russian language were sourced from various etymological dictionaries, dictionaries of foreign words, proverbs, and culinary dictionaries.

Data and analysis: The data for this study were collected from 70 Azerbaijani university students who are native Russian speakers. Among the participants, 40 had no prior knowledge or study of the Chinese language, while the remaining 30 had a foundation in Chinese.

Findings/Conclusions: The study found that among Azerbaijani college students, the words 'tea' and 'tofu' were the most commonly used borrowed words, with 80% and 72.9% mastery respectively. Overall, the study of Chinese loanwords in Russian in Azerbaijan has the potential to enhance and promote the development of the Russian language in the Azerbaijani socio-cultural context. The results of this study can provide insights into the effectiveness of language education and the need for improving the teaching of foreign loanwords in Russian.

Keywords: Russian language, Chinese loanwords, cooking and botanical terms, Azerbaijan, Chinese learners, non-Chinese learners.

INTRODUCTION

The evolution and adaptation of language is widely recognized as a fluid and dynamic process that is closely intertwined with societal developments. The fusion of two languages is a result of ethnic integration, involving the replacement of one language by another and the eventual extinction of the weaker language, with only a few elements surviving in the dominant language. Fusion is the gradual process through which distinct languages merge into a single language. When social groups speaking different languages come into close contact, their languages also come into contact, eventually leading to the transformation of one language for common use among individuals who originally spoke different languages. Language fusion is a complex and lengthy process that can manifest in various ways, including bilingualism, language substitution, and borrowing.

Language substitution, also known as 'assimilation', occurs when two languages merge and the dominant language replaces the weaker one. In this process, the social group speaking the weaker language switches to using the dominant language for most, if not all, communication. The dominant language evolves independently, incorporating certain elements from the weaker language while the weaker language eventually fades away.

Linguistic borrowing is a process through which a language assimilates linguistic elements from other languages, expanding its vocabulary. All languages inevitably borrow words from others, with native words tracing back to the earliest known stage while foreign words seamlessly integrate into the language. Interlanguage borrowing occurs when different social groups interact using various languages, often driven by shared

activities in economy, culture, and politics. Such changes are particularly evident in the lexicon of a language, as life and its surroundings are reflected in the words we use. The process of borrowing words from other languages is a natural and universal linguistic phenomenon that occurs in all languages. For instance, during the Han Dynasty, interactions with western countries through the 'Silk Road' led to the exchange of words between different ethnic groups. This resulted in the borrowing of words into the Chinese language, while also exporting certain terms to other languages. For example, the word 'silk' is referred to as 'seres' in Greek, 'silke' in Swedish and Danish, and 'szikai' in Lithuanian.

The interest in Chinese borrowings in the Russian language has significantly increased in recent decades due to the strengthening relations between the two countries and the growing number of lexemes of Chinese origin. As a result, the number of scientific papers dedicated to this layer of vocabulary is also on the rise.

Russian and Chinese linguists have approached the study of Oriental vocabulary from diverse perspectives. This includes analyzing the historical and etymological aspects of Chinese borrowings (Nesina 2014; Zhu & Liu 2005), investigating the reasons for their appearance in the Russian language (Zhou 2010), exploring the ways and types of their penetration into the Russian language (Shao 2011; Zhou 2010), analyzing thematic groups (Zhu & Liu 2005; Shi 2008; Wang 2008; Vykhovanets 2018; Yan 2017), and examining their formal and semantic adaptation (Kasimova 2014; Dong & Savilova 2016), studying the use and popularity of Chinese loanwords in Russian (Dong & Savilova 2016; Lin 2022). Additionally, the representation and semantic of Chinese borrowings in Russian dictionaries

and foreign words have been thoroughly researched (Yurii; Shao 2011).

By analyzing the above studies, Chinese loanwords in Russian can be roughly divided into the following categories:

1. names of dog breeds: Chow Chow, Shar pei, Shih Tzu, Pekingese;
2. names of Chinese kungfu: kungfu, taijiquan, wushu, qigong;
3. abstract concepts: Tao, Yin, Yang, Pinyin (transliteration), Mandarin, Fengshui;
4. natural phenomena: typhoon;
5. specific objects: wok, dajibao (newspaper), pearls, pipa (Chinese lute), fanza (house), hutong (alley), mahjong, qipao (chippao), book, kang, daba (coarse cloth), gohua (Chinese painting), banggu, nanka (Nanjing cotton cloth);
6. cooking and botanical terms: chai (tea), tofu, buuziy/manty (bun), lichi (lychee), ketchup, khandzha (prude), dimsam(dim sum), ramen, zhen'shen' (ginseng), kumkvat (kumquat), gaolyan (sorghum), tung(tung ford, or tung Chinese), apel'sin (orange), soya (soy);
7. Names of certain groups of people: hongweibin (guard), huanghuz (bandit), xodia(counter jumper).

Some of the Chinese borrowings listed above have historical significance, playing a role in specific periods, but have since fallen out of common usage in the Russian language. Examples include dajibao (newspaper), daba (coarse cloth), banggu, nanka (Nanjing cotton cloth), khandzha (prude), hongweibin (guard), huanghuz (bandit), and xodia (counter jumper). This paper focuses on Chinese borrowings that are still widely used in Russian or have been integrated into Russian words, particularly in everyday language and accessible to the general population, such as cooking and botanical terms.

This paper analyzes Chinese culinary and vegetative loanwords in Russian from an etymological point of view. It is also used as a basis to investigate the use and understanding of Chinese loanwords in Russian among Azerbaijani Russian-speaking university students (Azerbaijan University of Languages and Baku State University) and to investigate the acceptance of Chinese loanwords by the group of native Russian-speaking university students in Azerbaijan.

This study aims to explore the understanding of Chinese loanwords among Russian-speaking Azerbaijani university students (AUS) aged between 18-25 years old. Additionally, it seeks to highlight the practical and realistic importance of studying Chinese loanwords in the Russian language. This article explores Chinese-origin words related to domestic culinary and botanical spheres. The study draws from various etymological dictionaries of the Russian language, foreign word dictionaries, proverb dictionaries, and culinary dictionaries. These words are commonly used in daily life and are likely to pique readers' interest in their origin and history. Further more, these loanwords play a significant role in the Russian lexical system serving as a vital source for expanding its vocabulary.

This study collects data from two groups of college students: those who study Chinese and those who

are native Russian speakers without basic knowledge of Chinese. The research subjects will be asked to complete a questionnaire survey. The data collected will be analyzed using both quantitative and qualitative methods (MMR) to generalize and summarize the knowledge of Chinese source vocabulary among the two groups (from the Table 1: Mastery of Chinese loanwords in Russian by AUS).

The findings of the study suggest that AUS (Russian-speaking) have a good understanding of some Chinese loanwords in Russian such as *tea*, *ginseng*, *tung*, *kumquat*, *millet*, *sorghum*, *vermicelli* and other Chinese origin cooking and plant loanwords. Those who have basic knowledge of Chinese can distinguish more clearly between Chinese loanwords in Russian (*tea*, *sorghum*, *tofu*, *ginseng*, *vermicelli*). The study of Chinese loanwords in Russian in Azerbaijan can contribute to the enhancement and advancement of the Russian language within the Azerbaijani socio-cultural sphere.

The study of foreign loanwords has been a topic of interest for linguists for a considerable amount of time. Some scholars have highlighted the universal nature of this phenomenon, suggesting that it occurs when one language adopts linguistic elements from another language due to extralinguistic interactions between them. The process of borrowing is multifaceted continuous and intricate, involving the assimilation of an element from one language system into another. The popularity of loanwords is linked to the opportunity they provide for studying the level and state of social development in different historical periods. This analysis can reveal the linguistic essence of the external and internal world of people and research the evolutionary process of civilizations of different borrowing nations, ultimately tracing the general direction of their cultural development.

In this paper, we will analyze Chinese culinary plant loanwords in Russian from the perspectives of etymology and semantic development.

It has been noted Maslov (2005: 201) that economic, political and cultural interactions between nations are the basis for any borrowing process. Globalization has resulted in an increase in intercultural communication leading to the introduction of numerous new lexical elements, such as borrowed words, into the Russian language. In recent years, the friendly relationship between Russia and China has strengthened resulting in an increase of Chinese loanwords in the Russian language. These loanwords have become an integral part of Russian social life and reflect even the minutest details of modern life in China. In a paper by Prutskith (2020: 100), Chinese source loanwords have been categorized into political, cultural, social, economic, and ethnic perspectives. The paper lists four Chinese culinary plant representatives, namely "*ginseng*", "*sorghum*", "*chifan*" (Chinese restaurant), and "*tofu*", with "*ginseng*" and "*sorghum*" being classified as cultural Chinese loanwords and "*chifan*", "*tofu*" as social Chinese loanwords.

This study conducted a comprehensive analysis of 20 Chinese loanwords related to cooking and botany, which were extracted from recent research papers on Chinese loanwords in Russian. To gather information,

we consulted etymological online dictionaries of the Russian language and various internet sources such as Google and Yandex.

2.1. Cooking terms of Chinese origin

Chai (Tea)

The topic of Chinese loanwords in the Russian language has been extensively researched by scholars from diverse backgrounds, with a particular focus on the word *cha* "tea": the appearance and types of tea in Russian (Liu 2022; Zhu & Liu 2005; Dong & Savilova 2016; Vykhovanets 2018); tea-related derivatives (Nesina 2014; Kasymova & Gun 2017; Liu 2022); proverbs about tea (Kasymova & Gun 2017) and the evolution of the meaning of the word "tea" in Russian (Li 2019; Sen'ko 2019), etc.

Since ancient times, the Great Silk Road from China has transported a plethora of goods to Russia, including tea, which became popular primarily as a healing drink. The term "chai" was first documented in medical records in 1728 in Russian and was introduced to the Russian language through Turkish, Kyrgyz, and other Turkic languages as intermediaries from the Chinese word "cha". The word "chai" has become deeply ingrained in Russian folk culture as a commonly used term. Over time, this word has undergone semantic development within the Russian language: "tea drinking" (only singular form); "tea leaves"; "medicinal infusion of tea leaves"; "a drink infused with tea leaves" (Sen'ko 2019: 96). The well-known types of tea are: Oolong, Dragon Well tea, Pu'er, etc.

The numerous proverbs and sayings related to tea in Russian which demonstrates the language's proficiency with this term. Moreover, in Russian from the word "chai" formed verbs *chaevnichat*", "chainichat", "chaevat" (to have tea), nouns "chainik" (teapot), "chainitsa" (caddy), "chaevye" (tips), and "chaepitie" (tea ceremony), etc., which are used in spoken language.

Baikhovyi (Pekoe)

According to various sources (Zhu & Liu 2005; Vykhovanets 2018; Sen'ko 2019; Liu 2022; Vehi & Proshchenkova 2017), the term *Pekoe* is a Chinese borrowing. Vehi & Proshchenkova (2017: 64) suggest that the word «*baikhovyi*» originates from the Chinese term "baihuaye", which means "white birch leaves". However, it is believed by some that the name "baikhovyi" is derived from the Chinese term "bai hua", which translates to "white flower". Chinese "bai hua" is a type of Chinese tea making of the barely blooming tea leaf buds. *Pekoe* is one of the most popular teas known for its distinctive flavor and expensive value. It has been known worldwide since the late 19th and early 20th centuries. In the Soviet period, the word "pekoe" was used to describe high quality tea and was synonymous with high quality. Previously, the best was considered loose tea because it was immediately recognizable. However, over time, it lost its exotic appearance and the word "bai hua" gradually became Russified and transformed into "baikhovyi". Currently, the word in Russian has lost its real meaning and is used to denote different types of loose tea or tea of lower quality. Thus, the word "байховый" (baikhovyi) became an adjective in Russian.

Tofu

The word *tofu* has its origin in China, as evidenced by various studies (Zhu & Liu 2005; Dong & Savilova 2016; Vehi & Proshchenkova 2018; Vykhovanets 2018; Sen'ko 2019; Li 2019; Liu 2022).

The name "tofu" comes from the Chinese "dou fu", which means "bean curd". This kind of soy products have a rich history and can be traced back to two thousand years before our era. In 1990, the so-called Russian style *tofu*, also known as milk *tofu* with additives, appeared and gained popularity.

Buuzy, Manty (Bun)

These two words have their origins in China (Zhu & Liu 2005; Gorbatskaya et al. 2014; Dong & Savilova 2016; Vykhovanets 2018; Sen'ko 2019; Liu 2022). In traditional Chinese cuisine, steamed buns are referred to as "mantou," which translates to "barbarian's head." A dish with a similar name, "bao zi", emerged at the start of the 11th century. This name spread to Russia and nearby countries thanks to the Tatar-Mongolian army. Since then, this dish has become popular and adapted to various national cuisines. For instance, "buuzy" is a dish in Buryatian and Mongolian cuisine, its name comes from the Chinese "bao zi". In Central Asia, Turkey, and Mongolia, this dish is known as "manty" which is borrowed by Russian from Turkic languages from Chinese "mantou". This dish may have different names and come in various shapes (sealed and unsealed), sizes, and fillings, but its essence remains consistent.

Funchoza (Cellophane noodles)

Cellophane noodles is a threadlike food commonly found in Chinese cuisine (Dong & Savilova 2017; Vykhovanets 2018; Li 2019). It is a starchy product made of green peas or sweet potatoes and is known as "fen tiao" in Chinese. The word "funchoza" originated from "fen tiao" in the early 19th century. It is important to note that the Russian language has undergone morphological and phonetic changes in the word "funchoza".

Lichi (Lychee)

According to various sources (Zhu & Liu 2005; Gorbatskaya et al. 2014; Dong & Savilova 2017; Kasymova & Gun 2017; Vykhovanets 2018; Liu 2022), lychee is a word borrowed from the Chinese language. The word "lichi" originates from the Chinese term "lizhi" and has a rich history of cultivation and use in food and traditional Chinese medicine spanning over two thousand years. It is considered a culturally significant fruit in China and has been referenced by great writers. In the 17th century, lychee made its first appearance in Europe and was given the name "Chinese plum" by Europeans.

Ketchup

Ketchup is also a word of Chinese origin, as noted by Vykhovanets (2018: 36), Li (2019: 90), and Sen'ko (2019: 60). The word "ketchup" was introduced to Russia in the 1930s. In the 17th century, the word "ketchup" was borrowed into the English language from the Southwestern dialect of China. The pronunciation of the borrowed word was similar to the original Chinese term. In modern Chinese southwestern dialect, the syllable "ke" no longer refers to "salted fish", and "chup"-

"sauce", rendering ketchup obsolete in this region. While ancient Chinese ketchup was made from salmon, today's ketchup is predominantly tomato-based. The recipe for this sauce has changed completely.

Khandzha (Prude)

Another word that came to Russian from the northeastern dialect of the Chinese language at the beginning of the 20th century is "khandzha" (Jiang 2018; Li 2019; Liu 2022), which originally meant "bread and vodka". The exact time of its penetration into the Russian language is unclear, according to historical data, can be attributed to the period of Russian-Japanese war (1904-1905). The word "khandzha" underwent a semantic change in the Russian language. Nowadays, in colloquial speech, it is often used to denote insincere people and hypocrites.

Dimsam (Dim sum), a traditional Cantonese snack, is usually served with tea and refers to steamed dumplings with various fillings in small bamboo boxes. The word "dimsam" entered the Russian language through English, originating from the Cantonese dialect of China. In translation, "dimsam" means "dessert, light dishes" (Gorbatskaya et al. 2014; Jiang 2018; Li 2019).

Ramen

Ramen is a traditional pasta dish that originated in China (Gorbatskaya et al. 2014; Dong & Savilova 2017; Li 2019; Liu 2022). Historians suggest that the word "ramen" comes from the Chinese word "lamian" which means "stretched noodles". In Central Asia, it is pronounced "lagman". Ramen gained worldwide fame after the 1960s.

2.2. Botanical terminology of Chinese origin *Zhen'shen' (Ginseng)*

Ginseng is a Russian botanical loanword from the Chinese language, as stated by various sources (Wen & Proshchenkova 2017; Kasymova & Gun 2017; Vykhovanets 2018; Jiang 2018; Sen'ko 2019; Prutskith 2020). The word "zhen'shen" is a direct borrowing from the Chinese word combination "renshen", in which "ren" means person and "shen" means root. It is translated as "human root" because of its human-like appearance of this plant. The first mention of ginseng in Russia was found in 1677 in the book by Spafary N.G. (1677) "Description of the first part of the world, called Asia, in which the Chinese state with the other cities and provinces is located». In Russian the word "ginseng" also means a medicinal preparation on the basis of this plant.

Kumkvat (Kumquat)

The word "kumkvat" originates from its Cantonese name "golden orange" (Kasymova & Gun 2017: 1079), and it is also known by other names such as *Fortunella*, *Kinkan*, and *Chinese tangerines*. Kumquat holds the distinction of being the smallest citrus fruit in the world.

Chumiza (Millet)

Millet is one of the oldest crops in northern China (Kasymova & Gun 2017; Vykhovanets 2018; Sen'ko 2019). The word "chumiza" comes from the word "chou-mi-tsi" from Manchurian dialect, which means "millet, yellow rice". On the other hand, the word "chou-mi-tzu" was used as a derogatory term in 19th century in the Chinese colloquialism by locals in

the northeastern part of China. Nowadays in Russian spoken language the current meaning of this word refers to an unhygienic person (Zhu & Liu 2005: 33). According to historical data, this plant was cultivated on the territory of Russia after the Russian-Japanese War (1904-1905).

Gaolyan (sorghum)

Sorghum, a perennial herb belonging to the cereal family, is a word of Chinese origin (Vehi & Proshchenkova 2017; Vykhovanets 2018; Jiang 2018; Liu 2022). It originated from a consonant Chinese word that means "tall grass". The word "gaolyan" was introduced for the first time in the "Dictionary of foreign words included in the Russian language" by Chudinov in 1910.

Lokva (Loquat) is a Chinese loanword in the Russian language (Liu 2022: 57). It is also called *Rush Orange*. In modern times, loquat was introduced from Guangdong in 1784 and 1787 by the National Botanical Gardens of Paris in France and the Royal Botanic Gardens of Kew in England, and then spread to the Mediterranean coast of southern Europe and later to Russia. The word "lokva" originates from its Cantonese name "loquat" ("lo" - "plant, tree"; "quat" - "orange").

Tung (Tung ford, or Tung Chinese)

The tung tree was introduced to Russia from China in 1897 and played a significant role in Russia's industry during Soviet times (Liu 2022: 44). Etymologically, the name "tung" refers to the Chinese "tun-shu" ("tun" - "tree name", "shu" - "tree").

Apel'sin (Orange) - a Chinese loanword (Kasymova & Gun 2017: 1077). The orange which was brought to Europe from China in 1548 first caught the attention of Russian explorers in the early 18th century. In Russia, oranges are also known as *Pomeranian*, *Turkish apple*, *Naranj*, *Oranchor* (Lada, Khrustaleva). The word "apel'sin" has Dutch roots, which means "Chinese apple". The word "apel'sin" in Russian is a foreign language borrowing that has been fully integrated into the language. There are also several idiomatic expressions associated with oranges, for example: how a pig understands in oranges - about who does not understand completely; an orange in your glands - the expression of irritation, resentment; loading oranges with barrels - a lot of things.

Soya (Soy)

The word "soy" is considered an indirect borrowing in Russian from the Chinese language through the Japanese language (Sen'ko 2019: 63). According to «Explanatory Online Dictionary» (Ushakov 2008) and «the Russian etymological online dictionary» (Maksa 1964, 1987, 1996, 2006), it was borrowed from the Japanese language "shuyo", which was derived from the Chinese word "shu" (the common name for leguminous plants). In colloquial speech, the word "soya" is often used to denote a condiment, a spicy sauce made from the seeds of this plant. However, in Russian, this noun has recently acquired a negative connotation.

Chifanit (to Eat)

"Chifanit" is the only cooking-related verb introduced from Chinese, and its noun derivatives, "chifan" and "chifan'ka", emerged gradually. However, its usage in Russian is geographically limited (Yurii 2006; Li

2019; Bagdanov). This word originated from the Chinese verb "chi-fan" meaning "to eat" or "to nibble". Due to the popularity of Chinese cuisine among Russians, the slang term "chifanit" has gained traction in the cities of Siberia and the Far East. The word "chifanit" possesses a grammatical feature characteristic of the Russian language and expresses a person who takes a meal without proper table etiquette. Its derivatives, "chifan" and "chifan'ka", are often used to refer to Chinese restaurant.

2.3. Material summary

1. The author do not agree with the opinion of Vehi & Proshchenkova (2017: 64) that the Russian word "baikhovyi" is derived from the Chinese phrase "white birch leaves". Instead, the author argues that it is derived from the Chinese word "baihua", as supported by the Russian etymological dictionary.

2. Anise and mango have been mentioned in papers such as Zhu & Liu(2005: 32) and Kasymova & Gun(2017: 1078-1080) as Chinese plant culinary loanwords. However, the «Russian etymological online dictionary»(Maksa 1964, 1987, 1996, 2006) shows that the word "bad'yan"(anise) was introduced into Russia from the Tat language and is not a Chinese loanword. Similarly, the «Russian etymological online dictionary»(Shanskiy 1994,2000,2004.) shows that "mango" was introduced into Russian from Portuguese "manga" through English. In the Portuguese language the word "mango" originated from Tamil.

3. According to the «Russian online etymological dictionary»(Semyenova 2003) the meaning of mandarin as "citrus fruit" was introduced into Russian from French. However, the meaning of mandarin as "senior Chinese official" was transferred through Portuguese via German and other Western European languages. The study did not include the term Mandarin as it is not related to plant and cooking terms.

4. Scholars have different opinions on the origin of the Russian word "mintai"(walleye pollack), with some suggesting it is a loanword from Chinese culinary language, while others believe it is of Estonian-Finnish origin. According to the «Russian online dictionary»(Kuznetsov 2014) the word "mintai" is of Vietnamese origin.

5. The paper presents a list of 20 Russian culinary and botanical Chinese loanwords identified through inductive analysis, including 12 culinary terms such as *tea, prude, pekoe, cellophane noodles, buuzy(bun), manty(bun), ramen (lagman), dim sum, tofu, lychee, ketchup, and chifanit'*, and 8 plant terms such as *orange, ginseng, soy, sorghum, millet, kumquat, loquat, and tung.*

RESEARCH METHOD

The research methodology utilized in this paper focuses on the MMR strategy and incorporates both quantitative and qualitative analysis. (Robson, Colin 2011). The combination of quantitative and qualitative research methods has been utilized in scientific research for over fifty years. This approach is commonly used in sociological research and encompasses both positivist and humanist methodological orientations(Stavicka, Anna et al. 2019: 636).

The present study follows a pragmatic paradigm and employs the MMR framework to investigate the use of Chinese loanwords in Russian by Azerbaijani college students, with a specific focus on culinary and botanical terms. Both qualitative and quantitative methods are utilized to answer the research questions. The study incorporates data from different samples of respondents, including native Chinese learners and non-Chinese learners. An integrated approach is adopted to analyze the data sets in conjunction with each other.

This study employed questionnaires and interviews as its primary research methods. The participants were divided into two groups: the first group consisted of 30 Chinese learners (CL) who were native Russian speakers from the Chinese regional studies program and the senior class of the Confucius Institute at Azerbaijan Language University and Baku State University. The second group comprised of 40 non-Chinese learners (NCL) who were native Russian speakers from the Russian Department at the Philology Faculty of Baku State University. The survey was conducted at Azerbaijan Language University and Baku State University campuses, where 70 questionnaires were distributed, and 70 valid results were obtained.

Table 1

Mastery of Chinese loanwords in Russian by AUS

words of Chinese origin in Russian (culinary and botanical terms)	% of CL	words of Chinese origin in Russian (culinary and botanical terms)	% of NCL	words of Chinese origin in Russian (culinary and botanical terms)	% of total responses
tea	100%	tea	65%	tea	80%
sorghum	96.7%	tofu	60%	tofu	72.9%
tofu	90%	millet	55%	sorghum	61.4%
ginseng	83.3%	vermicelli	52.5%	ginseng	58.6%
vermicelli	66.7%	ginseng	45%	vermicelli	57.1%
dim sum	43.3%	kumquat	45%	millet	42.9%

Table 1

Mastery of Chinese loanwords in Russian by AUS

words of Chinese origin in Russian (culinary and botanical terms)	% of CL	words of Chinese origin in Russian (culinary and botanical terms)	% of NCL	words of Chinese origin in Russian (culinary and botanical terms)	% of total responses
to eat	43.3%	tung	45%	orange	41.4%
kumquat	40%	soy	35%	to eat	35.7%
tung	36.7%	sorghum	30%	dim sum	30%
millet	36.7%	to eat	30%	soy	28.6%
bun(manty)	36.7%	ramen	30%	bun(manty)	27.1%
ramen	20%	lychee	25%	ramen	25.7%
lychee	20%	bun(manty)	20%	lychee	22.9%
soy	20%	dim sum	20%	orange	12.9%
bun(buuzy)	16.7%	prude	12.5%	bun(buuzy)	10%
prude	6.7%	bun(buuzy)	10%	pekoe	5.7%
pekoe	6.7%	pekoe	5%	ketchup	5.6%
ketchup	6.7%	ketchup	5%	prude	5.6%
orange	3.3%	orange	5%	loquat	4.3%
loquat	3.3%	loquat	5%	kumquat	4.3%

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A study was conducted to assess the proficiency of Russian cooking and plant vocabulary among 30 CL and 40 N-CL individuals. The interviews were recorded and analyzed to obtain the results. After organizing and categorizing the questionnaire results, it was concluded that:

1. According to the survey, 80% of students believe that the word "tea" originated from Chinese, while only 7% thought it came from Russian. Students with a basic knowledge of Chinese language had a higher percentage of correct answers, with 100% knowing the origin of "tea", compared to 65% of students without a Chinese language foundation. Additionally, 6.7% of students were uncertain about the origin of the word "tea". In terms of "ginseng", 61.4% of students believed it originated from China, with 83.7% of Chinese language students knowing this to be true.

2. The majority of NCL respondents were not familiar with the terms "pekoe", "prude", and "sorghum". Only 4% of them correctly identified "sorghum" as a Chinese word based on its pronunciation, but were unable to provide its meaning. Some respondents mentioned that they had encountered the word "sorghum" in Mo Yan's work «Red Sorghum».

3. It was found that some students were unaware of the Chinese origin of "ketchup", "ramen", "manty", and "orange". 10% of the students believed that the word "ketchup" was of English origin, while 2.9%

thought that words "ramen" and "tofu" belonged to Korean. Additionally, some students believed that the word "bun(manty)" was Georgian and "bun"(buuzy) and "orange" were European in origin. There was also confusion about the origin of the word "prude", with some students believing it to be Arabic, and "lychee", which some believed to be Georgian.

CONCLUSION

Based on a comparative analysis of responses Chinese cooking and botanical borrowings in Russian can be classified into different recognition groups:

- 1) fully mastered (70—100 %): tea, tofu;
- 2) incompletely mastered (40—70%): tung, kumquat, millet, sorghum, vermicelli, ginseng;
- 3) partially mastered (10—40%): lychee, bun(manty), ramen, soy, dim sum, to eat, bun(buuzy);
- 4) not mastered(10% below): orange, loquat, pekoe, ketchup, prude.

The analysis reveals that students with basic knowledge of Chinese have a better understanding of some Chinese loanwords in Russian, including tea (100%), sorghum (96.7%), tofu (90%), ginseng (83.7%), and vermicelli (66.7%). The word "chifanit", commonly used in the Russian Far East region, has a regional character and is associated with the Chinese word "chi-fan" through its pronunciation by students with basic knowledge of Chinese (43.3%).

When attempting to identify the origin of words with non-Russian roots, local students often turn to neighboring countries such as Turkey, Georgia, and

Arab countries, as well as other non-Russian cultural circles. In addition, some respondents who lack Chinese language skills may mistakenly associate certain aspects of Chinese culture with Korean culture, such as tofu and ramen, due to the two countries' shared Confucian culture circle in East Asia and similar food cultures. This lack of in-depth knowledge about Asian culture can lead to cultural confusion.

Some respondents who studied Chinese mistakenly believed that "bamboo", "peony", "jasmine", and other important symbols of Chinese culture were words of Chinese origin. In reality, the word "bamboo" in Russian has Indonesian origins and "peony" is of ancient Greek origin. "Jasmine", on the other hand, originated from the Arabic language.

This survey and study on the use of Chinese cooking vocabulary and plant terms in Russian reveals that the majority of the Chinese loanwords listed are commonly used in daily life. However, with the exception of "tea" and "tofu", which are highly recognized and popular among Azerbaijani university students, most students do not pay much attention to the origin of Chinese-derived culinary and botanical vocabulary in Russian.

According to research, individuals with basic knowledge of the Chinese language tend to have a higher proficiency in recognizing Chinese loan words in Russian compared to those without such knowledge. This highlights the fact that learning Chinese not only helps learners acquire language skills and knowledge about Chinese culture, but also enhances their understanding and appreciation of their own native culture. Learning a new language can be seen as a process of assimilation, where the learner's internal cultural identity is influenced. In fact, learning multiple foreign languages can even lead to a deeper appreciation and respect for one's own culture, contributing to its development and enrichment.

In the questionnaire survey, it was found that all respondents showed a keen interest in the Chinese source borrowings of culinary botanical terms. Moreover, respondents who were learning Chinese language expressed that they had gained a new perspective on their native language through the examples presented in this study.

The borrowing of words between languages is a natural result of political, economic, and cultural exchanges between different communities. This process is not solely a linguistic phenomenon, but is also closely tied to the history, spiritual beliefs, and cultural values of the people in each country. In the case of Russian loanwords borrowed from the Chinese language, they have a positive connotation and serve various social functions, while also enriching the Russian vocabulary and contributing to the cultural identity of both countries. Therefore, studying Russian loanwords originating from Chinese in the context of Azerbaijani campus is of great practical importance.

Implications

This paper examines the use of culinary and botanical Chinese loanwords in daily language. However, it is important to note that some Chinese loanwords in Russian, such as "matan"(jaggery), "kalgan"(galanga),

"lyansin"(Dragon well tea), and "wula sedge", have lost their original meaning and are not included in this study. Additionally, while new words like "hotpot", "tanhulu", "dumplings", "fried dumplings", "sumai", "wonton", "kimchi", "white spirit", and varieties of tea such as "Oolong", "Pu'er", and "Dragon well tea" have gained popularity in Russia in recent years, they have not yet been included in the etymology dictionary and were therefore not investigated.

Abbreviations

AUS: Azerbaijani university students; MMR: Mixed-method research; CL: Chinese learners; NCL: Non-Chinese learners.

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